

CNN-LSTM regressor towards dexterous sEMG-based control of wearable hand exoskeletons

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Abstract—In recent years, the number of people with disabilities has increased hugely, especially in low- and middle-income countries. At the same time, robotics has made significant advances in the medical field, and many research groups have begun to develop low-cost wearable solutions. The Mechatronics and Dynamic Modelling Lab at the University of Florence has recently developed a new version of a wearable hand exoskeleton for assistive purposes. In this paper, we present a new regression-based strategy to predict the metacarpophalangeal angle position of each finger from the value of the sEMG signals capture on the forearm. Two Long Short-Term Memory models were compared, one in its standard configuration and the other with a convolutional layer, yielding significantly better performance for the second one.

Index Terms—Hand Exoskeletons, Electromyography, CNN-LSTM, Regression

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the most recent World Health Organization report, around 1.3 billion people — about 16% of the global population — experience a significant disability [1]. Nonetheless, people living in low- and middle-income countries have poor access to rehabilitation services, and in many of these countries, the density of rehabilitation-trained practitioners is often below 10 per 1 million population [2]. As a result of such considerations, creating a low-cost rehabilitation devices that are indeed user-friendly for even non-trained personnel is necessary to provide more people with a quality of life equal to unimpaired persons. Furthermore, hand does arise as one of the most valuable tool for mankind daily activities; within this context, several and distinct assistance devices, such as Hand Exoskeleton Systems (HESs), have been developed over the last few decades [3]. Among the wide of range of strategies dealing with HES control, the employment of surface ElectroMyoGraphy (sEMG) is emerging as one of most exploited technique for the sEMG acquisition ease and the uninvassiveness of the process. The sEMG signals are sampled on the forearm and used to recognize a set of hand gestures reproducible by the HESs [4], [5].

II. METHODS

A. MDM Lab Hand Exoskeleton System

Driven by these considerations, the researchers at the Mechatronics and Dynamic Modelling Laboratory (MDM

Lab) of the University of Florence have developed a portable, assistive exoskeleton for hand-impaired subjects, suitable in assisting people during their daily activities. As far as the design guidelines are concerned, the device has been realized so as to be easy to use and safe during everyday life, lightweight not to fatigue the user excessively and easily scalable for different limb sizes among subjects in order to be customizable on the specific user’s needs. Furthermore, to reduce costs and allow more people to access this technology, the device has been designed to be 3D printed using plastic materials.

Promising outcomes have been achieved [6], [7] and with the most recent prototype (Figure 1), the possibility of controlling each finger independently has been introduced as well. Such a crucial feature has let the previous control paradigm [8], [9], relying on just the classification of hand opening and closing through sEMG signals, to shift toward a finger-independent control based on a continuous regressor model.

In order to perform such a feature, the exoskeleton acts on each finger through a “rigid kinematic chain” that can be customized according to the user’s anthropometric dimensions, composed of three links which couple with the kinematic chain formed by the finger bones. The kinematic chain actively implements the flexion/extension of the MetaCarpophalangeal (MCP) joint while passively following its ab/adduction. Referring to Figure 1, each finger mechanism presents an electric motor (*orange*) connected to a gear transmission (*green*) which

Fig. 1: Most recent exoskeleton prototype designed by the Mechatronics and Dynamic Modelling Lab.

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Fig. 2: Overall architecture and specific structures of the CNN-LSTM (on the *left*) and LSTM-only (on the *right*) models.

acts directly on the rigid kinematic chain (*purple* and *cyan*). The single contact point with the finger is the end effector (*cyan*) pushing or pulling the finger to assist the user in the movements. The control loop is closed thanks to an encoder (*red*) that measures the flexion/extension of the MCP joint.

B. Regressor architecture

To deal with the aforementioned finger-independent control architecture, the authors have developed a novel regressor structure for the prediction of the finger flexion angles relying on sEMG data captured on the forearm and the finger angular positions measured in the previous instants. In particular, the overall strategy, reported in Figure 2, comprises of the sEMG data gathered from a Myo Armband by Thalmic Labs and the finger position supplied by the encoders placed on the HES. By exploiting such kind of information, the Deep Learning (DL) regressor model is able to map the sEMG-described user intentions into finger flexion angles acting as reference for the movement of the MDM Lab HES device.

As far as the DL model selection is concerned, a CNN-LSTM (Convolutional Neural Network - Long Short Term Memory) architecture has arisen as the optimal choice achieving the extrapolation of both spatial and temporal features. In fact, whereas spatial features allow to determine which muscle is activated, temporal characteristics provide information on how much and when that muscle was activated, leading to a more complete understanding of the forearm muscle activity. With the aim of arguing such a statement, the CNN-LSTM model has been tested against an LSTM-only network. For

what concerns the CNN-LSTM model a convolutional ConvLSTM1D layer with 128 units and a kernel size of two is followed by a standard LSTM layer with 64 units. Conversely, the LSTM-only network is composed of a first LSTM layer with 128 units followed by a second layer with 64 units. Finally, the output layer is realized by a dense layer that outputs a vector of five elements, representing the MCP flexion angle of each finger.

C. Dataset acquisition

Turning to the sEMG gathering process, the data have been segmented into 80-sample windows (400 ms) at 200 Hz of the sampling rate of the Myo Armband, with 30 samples (150 ms) of overlapping. This way, the delay that was introduced between one control signal and the next is equivalent to the time it takes to acquire 50 new samples (250 ms). For what instead concerns the sEMG feature selection, the combination of Root Mean Square (RMS) and Integral EMG (IEMG) emerged as the optimal combination in our case study.

Dataset generation is a delicate part of the training process of a DL algorithm, for this reason, a dedicated Graphical User Interface (GUI) (Figure 3) was developed to ensure proper formatting of the dataset file and facilitate its acquisition.

Because hand exoskeletons are extremely personal devices, they must be custom-designed from both a mechanical and control point of view. For that reason, a training dataset generated by a single subject performing an acquisition protocol that includes both full opening and closing movements and independent finger movements was considered in this study. The acquisition protocol was designed to acquire and synchronize sEMG signals and kinematic information on the angular position of the MCP joints of each finger. Another commercial sensor, the Leap Motion Controller by Ultraleap, was used to simulate the angular position signals sent by the encoders. We have estimated that the whole acquisition

Fig. 3: GUI overview. (a) User's name and surname. (b) 3D cube replicating the forearm's pose. (c) GUI commands and connection info. (d) Settings for the polar chart and the second function on the temporal plot. (e) Real-time sEMG evolution in temporal view. (f) Gyroscope and accelerometer data.

TABLE I: Metrics values for the presented models.

Model	Metrics	Value				
		Thumb	Index	Middle	Ring	Small
LSTM	MAPE	7.6596	0.5882	2.7816	0.5975	1.1663
	R2	0.4360	0.8848	0.7692	0.9002	0.7419
CNN-LSTM	MAPE	4.1307	0.4760	1.2120	0.3654	0.9568
	R2	0.6237	0.8660	0.8323	0.9436	0.8596

protocol can be performed in nearly two minutes, so the final dataset will have around 24,000 samples.

The obtained dataset was divided into two parts: the first 75% for training and the remaining 25% for testing. At each iteration of the training process, the data was further divided, and 20% of it was used to validate the model and check for overfitting.

III. RESULTS

The presented framework has been tested on a healthy subject by following a data acquisition protocol involving performing a series of hand openings, closings, and independent finger movements. Three complete opening and closing movements of all fingers, spaced out by a rest phase, and three complete flexions and extensions of each finger in sequence from the thumb to the small finger have been performed.

Furthermore, two metrics have been considered to evaluate the performance and compare the two selected DL models: mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) (Equation (1)) and R^2 score (Equation (2)):

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \left| \frac{\hat{y}_i - y_i}{y_i} \right| \quad (1)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (\bar{y} - y_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

where \bar{y} is the mean of the observed value y and \hat{y} is the vector of the predicted value.

As can be seen from Table I, the model with the CNN-LSTM layer leads to a significant improvement, especially for the thumb. From a quantitative perspective, by considering the MAPE values we can see an improvement for each finger, with an average increase of 36.27%; on the other hand, for the R^2 score, we have an average increase of 13.96%, with a just minimal decrease for the index finger (2.12%). As a summarizing statement, it is possible to notice that the CNN-LSTM predictions are, as a whole, more accurate with respect to the LSTM-only architecture; the possibility to learn additional spatial pattern does provide the DL model to predict improved movements from the sEMG signals.

From a qualitative perspective, the predictions performed with the CNN-LSTM architecture are visible in Figure 4. The graphs outlines the correct functioning of the proposed strategy by further highlighting that even with a low-cost

and low-density sEMG device, such as Myo, performing independent finger movement regression is indeed realizable by also exploiting the additional angular information supplied by the MDM Lab HES.

IV. CONCLUSION

The described research activity presents a novel DL-based control system for HES allowing the related patients to perform independent finger movement starting from sEMG data. The proposed DL-based regressor infers the finger flexion angles, supplied as HES angular reference values, starting from sEMG data, applied from a low-density device, such as the Myo Armband, and the angular positions at previous time steps provided by the MDM Lab encoders. Two distinct DL models have been selected and tested for such a HES control system (CNN-LSTM and LSTM-only) and the achieved outcomes have highlighted that adding a convolutional layer significantly improves the prediction performance.

As a far as the next stages are concerned, the whole architecture will be clinically tested with sEMG signals generated by impaired subjects, which are extremely different in terms of strength, structure, and intensity. Finally, the human-machine interface pattern will be studied: in effect, the behavior of subjects wearing the exoskeleton might evolve over time as they becomes more and more aware of the whole system and are, thus, able to generate signals more easily recognizable by the regression model itself.

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Fig. 4: CNN-LSTM regressor: in *blue*, the predictions performed by the network are highlighted, i.e., the estimated angular positions of the MCP joints, while in *orange*, their ground-truth values. (a) Thumb, (b) middle finger, (c) index finger, (d) ring finger, (e) small finger.